

Thoughts Brought By the Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Epidemic

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ABSTRACT: *The Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Pneumonia Epidemic is a major public health emergency since the founding of new China, which has brought great negative impact on people's production, life, study and work. After the epidemic is over, we should take a cut, grow our wisdom, mend our weaknesses, plug up loopholes, update our ideas, take precautions, strive to avoid the recurrence of such incidents in the future, ensure that the country's economy, society and other undertakings are "fast and stable", move forward steadily, and realize the Chinese dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation as scheduled.*

KEYWORD: *Novel coronavirus pneumonia epidemic, public health and epidemic prevention, ecological civilization construction, health awareness*

I. Introduction

The outbreak of novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) pneumonia epidemic in early 2020 was the most serious public health emergency that occurred since the founding of new China. It has the fastest speed of transmission, the most extensive infection, the most difficult control and the most serious loss. Fortunately, with the centralized and unified leadership of the CPC Central Committee, the institutional advantages of socialism with Chinese characteristics, the selfless dedication of the vast number of medical workers, and the strong cooperation of the whole nation in response to the call, after nearly three months of hard struggle, the people's war against the epidemic in Hubei Province has won a decisive victory. At present, the people of other countries in the world are under the leadership of their own governments in an unrelenting struggle against the Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Epidemic, and I believe they will soon win victory. The occurrence of the Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Epidemic is not accidental. We must reflect and summarize in time, learn lessons, scientifically find the cause of the outbreak, take precautions, take a multi-pronged approach, make up for shortcomings, plug loopholes, strengths and weaknesses, and strive to avoid such incidents happen again in the future, take fewer or even no detours, and reduce the cost of development, so as to ensure the continuous and high-quality development of economic and social undertakings in my country and other countries in the world,

and contribute Chinese wisdom and Chinese solutions to the steady development of the world economy and society.

1, Improve the major epidemic prevention and control system

First, strengthen monitoring and early warning. Closely around the goal of "early detection, early report, early isolation and early treatment", we will use the Internet, Internet of things, big data, artificial intelligence and other information technology means to strengthen the information collection, analysis and utilization ability of disease control and epidemic prevention institutions at all levels, and establish and improve multi-channel epidemic monitoring and rapid response systems, such as network direct report, public opinion monitoring, medical and health personnel report, scientific research discovery report, etc. We should speed up the construction of "public health and epidemic prevention blockchain", realize the information and data sharing of major epidemic risk monitoring and early warning, improve the collaborative mechanism of public health major risk research, assessment, decision-making and prevention and control, and improve the ability of major public health risk detection, reporting, early warning, response and disposal.

Secondly, improve the functional positioning. We should strengthen the capacity building of laboratories in disease control and prevention institutions, and give full play to the authoritative role of national and provincial laboratories in quarantine and inspection. Strengthen the technical guidance, personnel training, quality control, supervision and evaluation, performance appraisal and other functions of the municipal and county-level disease control and prevention institutions.

Finally, we should strengthen the construction of talent team and mobilize the enthusiasm, initiative and creativity of relevant talents. We should improve the policies on personnel training, access, use, treatment guarantee, assessment and incentive mechanism in disease control and epidemic prevention, establish a new operation mechanism combining guarantee and incentive, and appropriately improve the treatment of disease control and epidemic prevention personnel[1].

2, Strengthen the construction of public health colleges in China's medical universities

In the early stage of the epidemic prevention and control battle in Wuhan, the number of medical and epidemic prevention personnel was seriously insufficient, and the urgent need was only effectively relieved later with the strong support of medical and health care personnel from medical and health systems all over the country. In view of this, it is suggested that the central government and governments at all levels should take effective incentives in the future to promote the construction of public health faculties in medical colleges and universities in China to accelerate the improvement of quality and quantity, and attach great importance to the training of junior, middle and senior professionals in disease control and epidemic prevention, so as to meet the various types of talents required for conventional disease control and epidemic prevention and emergency disease control and epidemic prevention in China. While attaching importance to western medicine for disease control and epidemic prevention, we should also adhere to the parallel and coordinated development of Chinese and Western medicine, vigorously promote the culture of Chinese medicine, and develop the science of Chinese

medicine and the cause of Chinese medicine. Since the emergence of the novel coronavirus pneumonia epidemic, the National Health and Wellness Commission, together with the State Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine, has repeatedly issued treatment protocols for the novel coronavirus pneumonia, in which, based on the previous clinical treatment, Chinese medicine treatment protocols have also been given several times. From a practical point of view, Chinese medicine originates from the practice of treating and preventing diseases, and has been inherited and innovated over thousands of years of practice, and its attributes as a natural science are undeniable. As a "unique technique", TCM has the clinical advantages of "low side effects, radical cure and low cost"[2]. This "epidemic" practice proves once again that TCM has an irreplaceable and important role in the prevention and treatment of epidemics in disease control. Therefore, the state can introduce major initiatives to encourage and support the good and fast development of Chinese medicine in China, and vigorously promote the excellent Chinese medicine culture. It is suggested that public health colleges should be formed in all TCM universities in China to fully exploit the potential of TCM and give full play to its advantages in disease control and epidemic prevention, so as to make TCM's due contribution to disease prevention and treatment and to protect people's life safety and health.

3, Do a good job of routine hygiene and epidemic prevention in various public places

Public places are often crowded places, which are prone to and highly prone to public health incidents. Therefore, the state can develop and promulgate mandatory implementation standards, requiring the competent authorities of public places to introduce properties that meet the qualification requirements for public health services and management under the supervision and guidance of the relevant health prevention departments, and to do a good job of daily cleaning, disinfection and ventilation and other protective work in public places. In addition, public places also need to be equipped with a certain number of hand-washing pools and hand sanitizer to guide people in public places to develop the good habit of washing hands and hygiene. In large public places, such as schools, hospitals, vegetable farms, shopping malls, train stations, bus station waiting rooms, subway waiting platforms, airport terminals and other densely populated places, building facilities should have good natural ventilation design to ensure good ventilation, disperse germs and viruses, and improve the air health index. In addition, aircraft cabins, train cars, bus subway cars, etc., should also be equipped with ventilation and air circulation equipment, to ensure that the air in the alternating cycle of internal and external dilution of germs and viruses concentration, to enhance the freshness and health of the air.

4, Change the way and time of traditional meetings to reduce the probability of infectious diseases.

It is well known that there is a high degree of crowd gathering at meetings, and there is a risk of transmission of various infectious diseases. The central government and local departments, enterprises and institutions can start from the practical point of view, as far as possible to streamline the meeting, reduce the number of meetings. Indeed, because of the need to work, must open the meeting, can be used based on "5G Internet +" technology, held by video teleconference. The more important must be on site to open a large meeting, it is best to avoid the virus and the high incidence of influenza in the winter and spring. For example, the national "two meetings" can be held from the early March to mid-October each year in the autumn; local "two meetings" at all levels can be adjusted accordingly to between mid-to-late September and October each year. These two periods held "two

meetings", the General Assembly venue and the delegates live in the hotel, in general, do not need to open the air conditioning or cold, warm air system, moderate open doors and windows for natural ventilation can. This will kill two birds with one stone: not only can reduce the probability of infectious diseases, but also save energy, and really achieve the effect of moderate simplicity, green and low-carbon meetings.

5, Change the customs, change the eating habits of traditional combined meals, and advocate separate meals system to eliminate health hazards.

Influenced by traditional customs, the Chinese people are fond of the shared meal system, but from the health point of view there are many hidden dangers. In the process of sharing a meal, each person's saliva will enter the dish or soup with their chopsticks or spoons, and if there are sub-healthy people present, the bacteria, viruses or parasites carried by their saliva will take advantage of the opportunity to enter. According to the World Health Organization, saliva is one of the most important ways in which diseases are transmitted in all types of ways. For example, *Helicobacter pylori*, a spiral-shaped bacterium that "resides" on the gastric mucosa, is responsible for chronic gastritis and peptic ulcers, and is the main culprit of gastric cancer in humans. It is very easy to spread through saliva, food and utensils, and if an infected person shares a meal with others, it is likely to unknowingly infect healthy people. In addition, the habit of sharing meals and drinks is also an important reason for the high prevalence of hepatitis in the Chinese population. For example, hepatitis A, a typical digestive tract disease, is most likely to infect healthy people through body fluids and secretions. All these and more. Therefore, party committees and governments at all levels should study the spirit of General Secretary Xi Jinping's speech on "giving priority to people's health in the strategic development" and "implementing the health China strategy", and carry out activities to change customs and traditions among the people in a pleasing form to educate. In order to eliminate all kinds of potential health hazards, the government should promote the separate meals system by guiding the people to change their traditional eating habits.

6,Accelerate the pace of ecological civilization construction and increase the efforts of ecological civilization construction.

From the perspective of natural philosophy, both the many catastrophic viruses and plagues that have ravaged human history and the creation of this new coronavirus are related to mankind's wanton destruction of the ecological environment. The ecological environment is the condition of human survival and the foundation of human development. Whenever we should keep in mind that nature's ability to purify itself, its carrying capacity and other capabilities have limits, and once the limits are exceeded, it is bound to teach and educate humans in various special forms. Every time an epidemic occurs, it can be seen as a warning from nature to mankind[3]. In the face of nature's warning, human beings should not turn a blind eye, ignore it, or take a chance, but should be in awe of nature, and build a good ecological civilization with the spirit of time and urgency. The construction of ecological civilization requires a multi-pronged approach.

First, strengthen the education of citizens on ecological civilization. Continuously increase the dissemination of ecological knowledge and ecological education for all citizens. Knowing what is good is the only way to do what is good. Knowing and mastering the necessary ecological knowledge is a prerequisite for citizens to fulfill

their ecological responsibilities. The low ecological moral literacy of citizens is related to the lack of ecological education and ecological knowledge received. Governments at all levels should use various ways to strengthen the dissemination and education of ecological knowledge to citizens, and help all citizens to fully understand the ecosystem and the ecological responsibilities that humans should take. In this process, complex and profound theories should be simplified into a popular knowledge system with lively and visualized contents, so that ordinary citizens can hear, memorize and understand this knowledge and take it to heart. At the same time, the serious consequences of ecological damage should be presented to the audience, so as to awaken the ecological conscience of citizens with strong visual impact and stimulate their ecological consciousness, so that they can consciously reflect on and examine their needs, desires and behaviors in their real life and work practices, and then continuously correct their unreasonable needs, restrain their bad desires and reduce their blind behaviors, so as to realize the greening of their production, living and consumption methods. In addition, we need to create a green environment for all people through education. In addition, we must create a strong atmosphere of law-abiding for all people through education. To build a beautiful China and a beautiful world, we need to promote the construction of the rule of law for ecological civilization, gather the power of the people, enhance the concept of ecological rule of law for all people, and use publicity and education as an important tool to make people consciously comply with ecological laws. The use of ecological rule of law publicity and education to create a strong atmosphere for all people to abide by the law, so that all subjects form the concept of ecological rule of law, can feel the importance of ecological environmental protection, and strive to live in harmony with nature, feel the rule of law to help the far-reaching impact of environmental protection.

Secondly, strengthen top-level planning and design, adapt to local conditions, and make the construction of ecological civilization and the level of ecological governance the primary assessment indicator of the performance of local party committees and governments at all levels, which will be evaluated by the people and experts. Continuously strengthen the administrative enforcement of ecological civilization. Ecological environmental protection is a long way off, and to solve the difficulties of law enforcement and fundamentally restrain local governments from interfering with law enforcement, it is necessary to continuously increase administrative law enforcement, build a management mechanism to regulate government behavior, strengthen the environmental target responsibility system, and enhance the ecological awareness of local leaders and cadres through environmental accountability and performance appraisal mechanisms. Among them, the environmental protection assessment into the performance appraisal system, and according to this as an important basis for assessing the performance of cadres, promotions, to allow local leading cadres to establish a correct view of performance, reduce the improper intervention in ecological law enforcement of environmental protection departments, raise the threshold for investment projects, social and economic development must not be at the expense of the ecological environment. And the implementation of environmental accountability can allow local leading cadres to integrate the actual situation of local development, scientific decision-making, taking full account of environmental factors, to protect the environment on which the masses live. In addition, the

establishment and implementation of the accountability system can stimulate the responsibility sense of the local government and environmental protection departments in ecological protection, the separation of powers and responsibilities to be raised to a prominent position, by clarifying the powers and responsibilities of departments and personnel, so that the relevant staff forge a good work style, can fully consider the interests of the masses, taking into account the long-term development of the place.

Thirdly, the mobilization of the people's initiative, initiative and creativity, to fight a good pollution prevention and control of offensive, conventional, fine and protracted war, and actively participate in the whole process of ecological civilization construction. The domestic waste classification system formed on the basis of pilot projects in some provinces and cities should summarize the experience as soon as possible and speed up the full promotion and implementation in the country. The government can use economic and fiscal leverage to make domestic waste, industrial waste, construction waste and medical waste harmless, resourceful and reduced, to form a moderate and simple, green and low-carbon production and lifestyle, creating a beautiful environment and a healthy environment with green mountains and water, blue sky and green earth, clear air and clean soil.

7, Respect the objective law, play the subjective initiative, build a good health foundation and improve immunity.

It goes without saying that health is the greatest wealth. But it is easy to know and difficult to do. People are usually busy with their studies and work, their families and careers, and often do not raise their health to the height of attention it deserves. I believe this epidemic can make people feel the same way: health is the primary wealth! A healthy body is the capital, with which all kinds of dividends will be generated. Therefore, each of us should establish the consciousness of health first, and on the basis of respecting the basic laws of life movement, give full play to our subjective initiative, arrange our time rationally, lay a good health foundation, strengthen our immunity and resistance to prevent all kinds of viruses from attacking us. In general, the practice of building a good health foundation is: a reasonable diet, quit smoking and limit alcohol, moderate exercise, adequate sleep, and a calm mind[4]. Reasonable diet, that is, not to be partial, not picky, not overeating, through the three meals a day diet diversity, to achieve the purpose of balanced nutrition. Scientific research shows that smoking is harmful to health, while a small amount of alcohol, drinking low alcohol has certain health benefits, so we should advocate quitting smoking and limiting alcohol. Moderate exercise, that is, each person should choose the appropriate exercise time, exercise mode and the amount of exercise according to their own physical condition. At the opening ceremony of the 7th National University Games in 2007, Zhou Ji, the then Minister of Education of the People's Republic of China, on behalf of the Ministry of Education, proposed the concept of modern exercise and health to young students nationwide: "one hour of exercise every day, 50 years of healthy work and a lifetime of happiness". The call to "exercise one hour a day, live happily for a lifetime" is also applicable to the middle-aged and elderly. Regarding adequate sleep, there is no absolute standard for the amount of time needed, it varies from person to person. For adults, about 7 hours of sleep a day is usually

enough. To have a peaceful mind is to be positive, to live within one's means, to be happy with what one has; not to complain, not to grumble, to be reasonable, to think differently, to be understanding. The highest state is not to be discouraged, not to be sad, to be indifferent and clear, and to be quiet and far-reaching.

II. Summary

In conclusion, the Novel Coronavirus Pneumonia Epidemic has given people so much to think about. Through reflections and summaries, we should constantly enhance our awareness of the need for concern and prevention, make adequate preparations in advance, and do our best to avoid the recurrence and spread of similar outbreaks, so as to achieve good and rapid economic and social development in all countries around the world. Let's unite to build a community of destiny for human health, be confident, work together, prevent and control the epidemic scientifically and precisely, and win the battle against the new global epidemic as soon as possible!

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